

Free radical copolymerization of maleimides containing nitro-phenyl group with methyl acrylate

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Manuscript received 14 December 2009, revised 13 December 2010, accepted 13 December 2010

Abstract : *N*-(2-Nitro phenyl)maleimide (2NPM), *N*-(3-nitro phenyl)maleimide (3NPM), *N*-(4-nitro phenyl)maleimide (4NPM) and *N*-(2,4-dinitro phenyl)maleimide (2,4NPM) were synthesized and free radical copolymerization with methyl acrylate was carried out in THF at 65 °C using AIBN as a free radical initiator. The polymers were characterized by physical and spectral analysis. The thermal stability of copolymers was investigated by TGA. Effect of molecular structure of 2NPM, 3NPM, 4NPM and 2,4NPM on physical and thermal properties of their copolymers has been discussed.

Keywords : Free radical polymerization, nitro substituted maleimide, thermal stability, copolymers.

Introduction

High temperature polymer matrix composite can offer significant advantages over other material. Due to their low density and high specific strength, they are used in electronics, house hold, aircraft engines, rockets and other high temperature applications¹⁻³. These types of polymeric material are obtained by copolymerization of maleimides with vinyl monomers and found their application in many field such as aerospace, medical and microelectronic industries^{4,5} due to their heat resistant and mechanical properties⁶⁻⁹. In recent years, the homo and copolymerization of maleimides with vinyl monomers have been reported by several authors¹⁰⁻¹⁴. Such type of polymaleimide has drawback, their interactibility in imidized form and also difficulties in processing due to insolubility and infusibility. In polyimides only rigid maleimide ring present in polymer backbone which causes polymer processed difficulty due to their low solubility in solvents. In present work we studied the free radical initiate copolymerization of 2NPM, 3NPM, 4NPM and 2,4NPM with methyl acrylate. The physical properties of synthesized copolymers were studied for characterization

of copolymers. The spectral analysis was carried to confirm the structure of copolymers. The thermal stability was studied by TGA.

Results and discussion

The copolymerization of 2NPM, 3NPM, 4NPM and 2,4NPM with methyl acrylate was carried out at 65 °C in THF. Feed mol fraction of NPM, MA were 0.5 (*M*) each. Percentage yields are : 40.0, 41.1, 28.2 and 43.8 and intrinsic viscosity (dl/g) are 0.225, 0.202, 0.212 and 0.198 respectively.

The copolymers were soluble in THF, DMF, DMSO, 1,4-dioxane, acetone and ethyl acetate and insoluble in aromatic hydrocarbons, alcohols and water. The intrinsic viscosity of polymers was a measure of hydrodynamic volume and depends on molecular weight as well as size of the polymer coil in a given solution. Intrinsic viscosity (depends on mol. wt.) of C2,4NPM is higher than other copolymers due to higher molecular weight and higher molecular volume of the copolymer. The dependence of intrinsic viscosity on molecular weight of polymer is given by Kuhn-Mark Howind equation as : $[\eta] = KM^\alpha$ and

$$\log \eta = \log K + \alpha \log M.$$

In copolymerization of 2,4NPM and methyl acrylate, higher reactivity of methyl acrylate long chain polymer is formed so molecular weight of C2,4NPM is higher than other polymers.

The synthesized copolymers were characterized by FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectral analysis and IR spectral data are summarized in Table 1. The FT-IR and in the IR spectrum of all copolymers [copoly-*N*-(sub.-nitrophenyl)-maleimide-co-methyl acrylate], the maleimide unit was identified by the major characteristic absorption bands at 1790–1775 cm⁻¹, 1720–1705 cm⁻¹ (CO symmetric and asymmetric stretching of carbonyl group of imide ring), 1530–1540 cm⁻¹ (CH=CH aromatic ring), and 1340–

air up to 200 °C/min.

Tables 2 and 3 reveals that copolymer C4NPM is more stable than others on basis of initial decomposition temperature (*T*_i) and degradation data. The copolymer C4NPM is more stable than other copolymers due to higher reactivity of maleimide unit in copolymerization. The higher content of maleimide is present in copolymer, which have more thermal stability than others. It also depends on substitution in phenyl ring and reactivity of maleimide monomer in polymerization. The higher content of maleimide unit is present than copolymer is stable due to rigid imide ring, which has not degrade at higher temperature. The results of percentage weight loss suffered from 100 °C to 600 °C at 100 intervals are furnished in

Table 1. FT-IR spectrum of the copolymer shows bands at

C2NPM	C3NPM	C2,4NPM cm ⁻¹	C4NPM	Type of vibration
1780, 1710	1790, 1720	1778, 1709	1780, 1710	C=O sym. and asym. stretch of imide
1540	1548	1538	1540	C-NO ₂ stretch
1340	1320	1335	1340	C-N stretch of <i>N</i> -sub. maleimide
1528	1528	1518	1520	C-H stretch of aromatic ring
650	630	647	623	C-H bending of <i>cis</i> CH=CH
2910	3050	2962	2910	C-H stretch of -CH ₃
1120	1189	1183	1120	C-O-C stretch of ester

1320 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretch of imide ring). Characteristic for methyl acrylate monomer unit in polymer is the IR bands at 1189–1120 cm⁻¹ due to C-O-C stretch of ester group. It's confirmed that both monomeric units are present in copolymers and imide ring remained intact during copolymerization.

In the ¹H NMR spectrum of all copolymers [copoly-*N*-(sub.-nitrophenyl)maleimide-co-methyl acrylate], the maleimide unit were identified by signals at δ 7.0–8.5 ppm from aromatic protons. The δ at 3.0–4.0 ppm due to formation of flexible -[CH-CH]_n- and -OCH₃ group of methyl acrylate unit. To the protons of -CH₂- and -CH- were assigned signals at 1.00–2.1 ppm.

The thermal stability of copolymers were determined by TGA in air atmosphere at heating rate at 10 °C/min. The thermal stability data are given in Tables 2 and 3. Synthesized copolymers show good thermal stability and did not show any change in appearance when heated in

Table 2. Thermal behavior of copolymers

Polymer	Degradation step	<i>T</i> _i (°C)	<i>T</i> _{max} (°C)	<i>T</i> _f (°C)	Residue at 500 °C
C2NPM	I	212	270	315	8.14
	II	315	420	540	
C3NPM	I	213	360	448	27.18
	II	448	500	560	
C2,4NPM	I	210	395	442	4.85
	II	442	480	560	
C4NPM	I	217	292	345	15.01
	II	345	398	550	

Table 3. Percentage weight loss of copolymers at various temperatures

Polymer	Weight loss (%)			
	200 °C	300 °C	400 °C	500 °C
C2NPM	0.75	68.92	73.85	91.86
C3NPM	0.76	10.64	40.88	73.82
C2,4NPM	1.01	12.45	81.67	95.15
C4NPM	0.72	7.73	50.73	84.99

Table 4 and reveals that weight loss was below to 0.5–3% up to 200 °C in all copolymer samples. The residual mass at 500 °C is more in C3NPM and C4NPM.

Table 4. Synthesis and characteristics of *N*-(sub.-nitro phenyl)-maleimide

NPM	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%)		
		C	H	N
2NPM	70	55.0	2.32	12.19
3NPM	75	54.78	2.51	12.27
2,4NPM	68	47.97	1.97	11.11
4NPM	80	54.92	2.31	12.27
Theoretical for C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₄ N		55.05	2.75	12.84
Theoretical for C ₁₀ H ₅ O ₆ N ₂		48.19	2.01	11.24

The properties of polymer are depending upon the polymer chain and content of composition of maleimide monomer. The reactivity of monomer in polymerization is depending on structure and position of substituted group in phenyl ring. Monomer 2,4NPM shows lower reactivity in polymerization due to two bulky group present in phenyl ring and steric hindrance of group. 4NPM has shown higher reactivity than other synthesized monomers due to less steric effect during polymerization. The thermal properties of polymer are increased with increasing maleimide content in polymer back bone which have depend on reactivity of maleimide unit.

Experimental

Substituted nitroaniline and maleic anhydride were recrystallized from acetone. Methyl acrylate was shaken two to three times with 5% NaOH to eliminate hydroquinone inhibitor and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ for 6 h and distilled¹⁵. The head and tail fractions were discarded. Methanol used in the present work was of analytical grade and were used as received.

Measurements : ¹H NMR spectra of monomer and polymer samples were taken in DMSO-*d*₆ on a Bruker DPX-200/DPX-300 spectrometer at 200/300 MHz. The internal reference used was TMS. FT-IR spectra of the monomer and polymer sample were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC (4000–400 cm⁻¹) FT-IR spectrometer, using KBr pellet technique. Solubility is measured in various solvent. 100–200 mg samples of finely grounded polymer were placed into small test tube and 5 ml of each type of solvent was added and then stirred at 30 °C for

some time and nature of polymer in solvent was studied. The viscosity measurements were carried out in DMF at 30 ± 0.2 °C, using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. The thermograms in air were obtained on a Mettler TA-3000 system, at a heating rate of 10 °C/min from 0 °C to 600 °C.

N-(Sub.-nitrophenyl)maleimide were prepared by reaction of maleic anhydride with 2-, 3-, 4-, and 2,4-nitro aniline, followed by cyclodehydration of the resulting maleimic acid according to previous published procedure¹⁶.

The copolymerization of 2NPM, 3NPM, 4NPM and 2,4NPM in a solution of THF was carried using AIBN as a free radical initiator at 65 °C. After a prescribed time the mixture was poured into a large amount of methanol to precipitated the copolymer. The crude product was reprecipitated from THF solution into methanol. The process of dissolving and precipitation is repeated twice to get rid off unreacted monomer. Finally product was filtered and dried in vacuum at oven at 50 °C.

Conclusion :

The free radical copolymerization of *N*-(sub.-nitro phenyl)maleimide with methyl acrylate was carried in THF at 65 °C. The copolymers were characterized by intrinsic viscosity and solubility test. The structure was confirmed by FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectral analysis. The thermal stability is determined by TGA and it depends on substitution of phenyl ring. The effect of substitution of nitro group in polymerization, physical properties and thermal stability was also studied.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to CDRI, Lucknow and SICART, Vallabh Vidyanagar for analysis work.

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